

1 **Assessing the oxidation of imidacloprid insecticide through the**
2 **Cu(II)/PMS homogeneous process**

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18

19 **Abstract**

20

21 Water contamination by synthetic organic compounds is one of the major environmental
22 issues facing the world today. Among the available methods to treat them, catalytic
23 advanced oxidation processes using Cu(II) ions to activate peroxymonosulfate is a
24 potential candidate at slightly alkaline conditions (pH 8). In this work, we investigated
25 the influence of PMS concentration (0-1000 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$), solution pH (7-10), and the
26 effect of water matrix (ultrapure, tap, and simulated municipal wastewater - SMWW) on
27 imidacloprid (IMD) insecticide oxidation. After optimization of the investigated
28 variables (500 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ PMS and pH 8), almost complete IMD oxidation was achieved
29 in 6 h using ultrapure and tap water. The main detected byproducts resulting from IMD
30 oxidation in ultrapure water are due to hydroxylation reactions and rupture of the
31 imidazolidine ring. When SMWW was used, IMD oxidation was only 10% in 6 h,
32 probably due to the scavenging effect of inorganic and organic compounds. The main
33 produced working oxidants were radical (mainly HO^\bullet and $\text{SO}_4^{\bullet-}$) and non-radical ($^1\text{O}_2$,
34 Cu(I), and Cu(III)) species, based on scavenging experiments and mass spectrometry
35 detection of produced DMPO byproducts. Among these, HO^\bullet and to a less extent
36 Cu(III) species seems to promptly oxidize IMD.

37

38 **Keywords:** Advanced oxidation process; homogeneous catalysis; emerging
39 contaminants; *in situ* chemical activation

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42 1. Introduction

43

44 Water contamination by synthetic organic compounds coupled to climate change
45 stands as the most threatening challenges that must be dealt with in the few years to
46 come [1,2]. These issues have the potential to cause damage to ecosystems and harm to
47 human health with deleterious consequences to the world economy [3]. Moreover, poor
48 water quality can also lead to health problems [4] due to chronic exposure to persistent
49 organic pollutants (POP's), such as antibiotics, insecticides and so on [5].

50 To tackle the problem of POP in surface water, it is crucial to develop treatment
51 methods that incorporate newly engineered materials [6–8]. Advanced oxidation
52 processes (AOPs) are a collection of techniques that have garnered considerable interest
53 due to their ability to address environmental issues like the removal of organic
54 pollutants from water [9]. The broad applicability of AOPs is attributed to their ability
55 to generate highly oxidizing radical species like hydroxyl (HO^\bullet) and sulfate ($\text{SO}_4^{\bullet-}$),
56 primarily through the activation of peroxy-derived chemicals like hydrogen peroxide
57 (HP, H_2O_2), peroxydisulfate (PDS, $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$), and peroxymonosulfate (PMS, HSO_5^-) [10–
58 12]. Given the high reactivity of these radical species through electron transfer,
59 hydrogen atom abstraction, or electrophilic addition, side reactions with inorganic
60 (halides and oxyanions) and organic (humic acids) compounds could result in lower
61 efficiencies in the oxidation of POP's [13]. On the other hand, non-radical species such
62 as singlet oxygen ($^1\text{O}_2$) could offer high selectivity through electrophilic addition
63 reactions to unsaturated moieties at the expense of slower pollutant oxidation kinetics
64 [14,15].

65 Alternatively, the use of metal ion, namely Co(II) or Cu(II) can also lead to a
66 range of radical species, particularly when PMS is used as the oxidant to be activated,

67 resulting in high oxidation rates of organic compounds [16,17]. Previously, Anipsitakis
68 and Dionysiou [18] investigated the potential of nine transition metal ions (Ag(I),
69 Ce(III), Co(II), Fe(II), Fe(III), Mn(II), Ni(II), Ru(III), and V(III)) towards activation of
70 PMS, PDS, and HP and, Cao et al [17] recently revisited the proposed mechanism of
71 Co(II) mediated activation of PMS and thus highlighted the potential role of Co(III)
72 species, besides HO^\bullet and $\text{SO}_4^{\bullet-}$ species, to oxidize carbamazepine. Ou et al. [19]
73 demonstrated that the addition of trace amounts of Cu(II) notably enhances the catalytic
74 performance of the Fe(III)/peroxymonosulfate (PMS) process when borate buffer is
75 present. Wang et al. [20] reported that Cu(III) was the primary and selective
76 intermediate oxidant species produced during PMS activation by Cu(II) ions, in addition
77 to HO^\bullet and $\text{SO}_4^{\bullet-}$ species. In a recent paper [21], our group also reported the key role of
78 leached Co(II) ions from CoFe_2O_4 magnetic ferrite to oxidize imidacloprid insecticide
79 towards PMS activation even at low values of Co(II). Similar results concerning the role
80 of low amount of dissolved transition metal ions towards PMS activation was noticed
81 by Wang. et al. [22]. However, there is still a lack of understanding regarding the
82 relationship between the working oxidant species, especially those derived from Cu ions
83 [23], and the effects of operational variables to degrade (micro)pollutants. These
84 variables include metal ion concentration, pH values, and the type and concentration of
85 buffer used during PMS activation.

86 Thus, the aim of the present work is to investigate the influence of Cu(II) ions on
87 the activation of PMS, leading to the production of both radical and non-radical species
88 (including those derived from Cu ions) that oxidize the insecticide imidacloprid. This
89 includes examining the effects of *in situ* produced Cu(I) and Cu(III) ions. For such, the
90 effect of PMS concentration, solution pH, and main produced working oxidants using
91 scavenging compounds or spin probes were investigated. All byproducts resulting from

92 IMD oxidation were analyzed using liquid chromatography coupled with mass
93 spectrometry. The findings are in line with previously published research, highlighting
94 the secondary role of Cu ion species, along with mainly HO[•], in the oxidation of
95 organic compounds.

96

97 **2. Materials and methods**

98

99 *2.1 Chemical reagents*

100

101 Chemical reagents, including IMD (Imidacloprid, see chemical structure in Fig.
102 S1 – from Milenia Agrociencias S/A), CuSO₄•5H₂O (analytical grade reagent, a.r.,
103 Synth), NaOH (a.r., Panreac), Na₂B₄O₇•10H₂O (a.r., Merck), K₂HPO₄ (a.r., Sigma
104 Aldrich), H₂SO₄ (a.r., Merck), Na₂S₂O₃•5H₂O (a.r., Synth), PMS (potassium
105 peroxymonosulfate, a.r., available as Oxone[®], Sigma Aldrich), KI (a.r., Synth), NaHCO₃
106 (a.r., Sigma Aldrich), DMPO (5,5-dimethyl-1-pyrroline N-oxide, a.r., CaymanChem),
107 Neocuproine (NCP: a.r., Sigma Aldrich), NaIO₄ (a.r., Sigma Aldrich), isopropyl alcohol
108 (IPA: 99.8%, Panreac), t-butyl alcohol (TBA: 99.7%, Neon), furfuryl alcohol (FFA: a.r.,
109 Sigma Aldrich), L-histidine (L-H: a.r., Sigma Aldrich), HCOOH (a.r., J.T.Baker),
110 CH₃OH (HPLC grade, JTBaker) were used as received without prior treatment. All
111 solutions were prepared using deionized water (Millipore Milli-Q Direct-Q[®] 5 UV
112 system, $\rho \geq 18.2$ M Ω cm).

113

114 *2.2 IMD oxidation and analysis of treated solutions*

115 The oxidation of IMD (50 mg L⁻¹) by the *in situ* chemical activation of PMS
116 using Cu(II) was carried out in a water jacket glass vessel (150 mL) under magnetic

117 stirring in the dark. First, 100 mL of a buffered solution (10 mmol L⁻¹ of KH₂PO₄ at pH
118 7 or Na₂B₄O₇ at pH 8, 9 and 10) was added to the reaction vessel followed by the Cu(II)
119 solution. Immediately, solid PMS was also added to start the oxidation reaction. The
120 effect of different parameters such as PMS concentration (250, 500, and 1000 μmol L⁻¹)
121 and solution pH (7, 8, 9 and 10) were studied. The solution pH was continuously
122 monitored and manually adjusted by adding diluted H₂SO₄ or NaOH solutions. Other
123 operational variables, such as Cu(II) ion concentration, the treatment time, solution
124 temperature, and stirring were kept constant at 800 μg L⁻¹, 360 min, 25 °C, and 600
125 rpm, respectively. The analysis of the effect of Cu(II) ions on the PMS activation (500
126 μmol L⁻¹) was carried out previously [24] in slightly alkaline solutions (pH 8), allowing
127 for analysis on the effect of leached Cu(II) ions from CuFe₂O₄ magnetic ferrite. In this
128 work, the activation of PMS did not occur with the use of 25 to 100 μg L⁻¹ of Cu(II)
129 ions. After a second trial, the amount of Cu(II) ions required to activate PMS was found
130 to be 800 μg L⁻¹, which agrees with the work of Wang et al. [20].

131 The samples were analyzed after being collected from the reaction mixture at
132 predetermined time intervals and quenched with excess Na₂S₂O₃ (1.0 mol L⁻¹), except
133 when the residual oxidant was quantified.

134 After the initial optimization with ultrapure water, tests were conducted on tap
135 water and a simulated municipal effluent wastewater (SMWW) to evaluate the impact of
136 typical inorganic and organic interferences in real-world scenarios. The characterization
137 and composition of these water matrices can be found in Table S1, S2, and Text S1.

138 The concentration of IMD was analyzed using a high-performance liquid
139 chromatography (HPLC) instrument (Shimadzu 20A) at 270 nm using a core-shell C-18
140 reversed-phase column as the stationary phase (150 mm × 4.6 mm i.d., 5 μm particle
141 size, 100 Å pore size, from Phenomenex®). A mixture of aqueous 0.1% (V/V) formic

142 acid (eluent A) and methanol (eluent B) was used as the mobile phase in a gradient
143 elution mode (from 20% to 90% of B in 8 min and then, back to 20% after 2 min and
144 keeping this condition for 2 min before further analyses). The flow rate, injection
145 volume, and temperature of the column were kept fixed at 1.0 mL min^{-1} , $25 \text{ }\mu\text{L}$, and 24
146 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, respectively.

147 Ultra-high performance liquid chromatography coupled to a time-of-flight mass
148 analyzer (UHPLC-QToF MS) was used under optimized conditions to analyze
149 intermediates formed during the IMD oxidation process, according to a methodology
150 described in Text S2 and Table S3. After determining the chemical structure of
151 byproducts, their toxicity was assessed using the ECOSAR software. The
152 chromatographic procedures to determine carboxylic acids and inorganic ions can be
153 seen in Text S3.

154 The amount of residual oxidant was determined using the spectrophotometric
155 method adapted from the work of Liang *et al.* [25]. Briefly, 2.0 mL of a 0.6 mol L^{-1} KI
156 and 0.06 mol L^{-1} NaHCO_3 solution were added to 1.0 mL of the sample. The resulting
157 solutions was shaken by hand and allowed to stand for 15 min before analysis in a UV-
158 Vis spectrophotometer (Shimadzu UV-1800). The spectra were obtained in the range of
159 200 to 400 nm and the analysis was performed at a wavelength of 352 nm .

160 The main working oxidant species were assessed by *i*) UHPLC-QToF MS
161 analyses using a DMPO solution as the spin probe (see Text S4 for details), *ii*)
162 scavenging experiments using isopropyl alcohol, t-butyl alcohol, furfuryl alcohol at 50
163 mmol L^{-1} , neocuproine at $50 \text{ }\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$, sodium periodate at $25 \text{ }\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$, and potassium
164 bromide (10 and 100 mmol L^{-1}) and *iii*) measurement of dissolved oxygen to account
165 for the produced $^1\text{O}_2$ species.

166

167 3. Results and discussion

168

169 3.1 Effect of operational variables ([PMS] and pH) and water matrix

170 Fig. 1a shows the effect of PMS concentration on the oxidation of IMD. As
171 expected, high concentration values of PMS led to increasingly high values and rates
172 (from $4.4 \pm 0.9 \times 10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$ using $250 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ of PMS to $23 \pm 2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$ at 1000
173 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ of PMS – see Table S4) of IMD removal. Oxidation levels higher than 90%
174 were only attained when PMS values higher than $500 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ of PMS were used. An
175 interesting result was observed when PMS consumption was analyzed, as shown in Fig
176 1b, *i.e.*, all investigated PMS concentrations led to similar percentages of consumption.
177 That behavior could lead to misinterpretations since the amount of PMS consumed was
178 increasingly high. Another interesting result refers to the important role of Cu(II) ions to
179 activate PMS since the sole use of Cu(II) ions (see green symbols of Fig 1a) or PMS
180 (see orange symbols of Fig 1a) was unable to oxidize IMD.

181 The effect of pH using the borate buffer was investigated from 8 to 10 in the
182 presence of $500 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ of PMS, as shown in Fig. 2a. Similar oxidation rates (11.8
183 $\pm 0.9 \times 10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$ and $15.3 \pm 0.6 \times 10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$ at pH 8 and 9, respectively, see Table S5)
184 and complete oxidation of IMD after 6 h were obtained. When alkaline solutions (pH
185 10) were assessed, the oxidation rate increased abruptly ($6 \pm 1 \times 10^{-2} \text{ min}^{-1}$) due to the
186 generation of $^1\text{O}_2$ oxidant species (Eq. 1), as the pH of the solution is higher than the
187 second $\text{p}K_{\text{a}}$ (9.4) [26] value of PMS

188

190

191 Activation of PMS from acidic to neutral solutions (see black symbols for pH 7)
192 using phosphate buffer was not observed. Thus, the remaining experiments were carried
193 out under pH 8, as this condition is close to neutral conditions, in the presence of 500
194 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ of PMS. Under these circumstances, the application of PDS was evaluated (as
195 shown in Fig. S2), but it resulted in neither oxidation of IMD nor consumption of the
196 oxidant. This behavior aligns with expectations, given that the reaction rate between
197 PDS and Cu(II) is characteristically slow.

198 The investigation of how differently water matrices can affect PMS activation is
199 shown in Fig. 3. The use of tap water had a similar oxidation level and a similar
200 oxidation rate when compared with ultrapure water, probably due to the low amount of
201 inorganic and organic (no detectable dissolved organic carbon) species. The slightly
202 higher oxidation performance when using tap water is due to residual chlorine (see
203 Table S1). On the other hand, only a slight IMD oxidation (10% in 6 h) was attained
204 when the SMWW was used. This behavior is attributable to the presence of inorganic
205 and organic interferences that consume the produced oxidants (see discussion below), as
206 observed in the work of Wang et al. [27].

207

208 **3.2 Oxidation byproducts and pathways of IMD degradation**

209 To investigate the main produced oxidation byproducts from IMD degradation,
210 UHPLC-QToF MS measurements were carried out using ultrapure H_2O in the
211 optimized conditions, *i.e.*, $800 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ ($12.5 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$) Cu(II) ions and $500 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$
212 PMS at pH 8 (buffered with 10 mmol L^{-1} of $\text{Na}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$). As evident from Table S6
213 (listing the main detected intermediates along with their retention times and
214 fragmentation ions) and Fig S3a (illustrating the evolution of the primary extracted
215 ions), four intermediate compounds were consistently detected in the solution during the

216 entire 6 h treatment period, in addition to IMD. The MS/MS spectra and proposed
217 fragmentation route of the main detected intermediates can be seen in Fig. S3b-S3f and
218 S4, respectively. Based on the proposed intermediate compounds, three degradation
219 pathways can be inferred and are depicted in Fig. 4: *i*) rupture of the imidazolidine ring
220 (yielding product P1), *ii*) consecutive hydroxylation reactions on the imidazolidine ring
221 (resulting in P2 and P3), and *iii*) complete loss of the imidazolidine ring (leading to P4).
222 In previous work of our group [24], the same intermediate compounds were detected
223 using CuFe_2O_4 for the *in situ* chemical activation of PMS. The theoretical ecotoxicity
224 prediction of the main detected IMD byproducts using the ECOSAR (Ecological
225 Structure Activity Relationship) software slightly decreased when compared to the
226 parent compound, as shown in Table 1, due to hydroxyl addition reactions [28] and
227 rupture of the imidazolidine ring. Moreover, it is expected that the concentrations of
228 IMD and its primary byproducts will remain below the reported LC_{50} and ChV
229 concentration values obtained using ECOSAR after a 6 h treatment period. Wang et al.
230 [29] explored the oxidation of IMD using ferrate (VI) ions across a pH range of 6 to 9,
231 employing various water interferences. Consistent with their findings, the toxicity of
232 intermediate compounds (specifically, the P2 and P4 oxidation byproducts) decreased
233 during treatment, and IMD underwent complete oxidation within a matter of minutes.
234 Voigt et al. [28] also observed a decrease in toxicity of IMD oxidation byproducts, after
235 a photolysis process caused by hydroxylation reactions using the ECOSAR software. A
236 study by Bai et al. [30] demonstrated that a heterojunction photocatalyst made of carbon
237 quantum dots, BiFeO_3 , and BiOBr can effectively activate PMS to oxidize IMD. This
238 process achieved complete degradation of IMD within 3 hours, and, importantly, the
239 byproducts produced (hydroxylated and resulting from rupture of the imidazolidine
240 ring) were less toxic and mutagenic compared to the original IMD. This indicates that

241 these methods could be a promising approach for reducing environmental pollution
242 caused by IMD.

243

244 **3.3 Working oxidants**

245 To verify the existence of HO• radical species in the reaction medium during
246 PMS activation by Cu(II) ions, DMPO was used as a scavenger. The primary
247 byproducts resulting from HO• addition reactions were assessed using UHPLC-QToF
248 MS measurements, as outlined in Text S4. Electron spin resonance was also carried out
249 but led to inconclusive findings. As can be seen in the total ion chromatogram of Fig S5
250 and Table S8, the main detected byproducts were assigned to DMPO/2OH and
251 DMPO/OH as well as dimers mainly resulting from hydrogen atom abstraction, *i.e.*,
252 2DMPO/O-3H, 2DMPO/-H, and 2DMPO/-3H. The MS/MS spectra and proposed
253 fragmentation route for the DMPO-derived compounds are reported in Fig. S6 and S7,
254 respectively. Despite clear evidence on the presence of HO• species and its superior
255 kinetic constant with DMPO ($1.9\text{-}3.3 \times 10^9 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ [31] in comparison to 2.7×10^{-2}
256 $\text{L mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ for the reaction with $\text{SO}_4^{\bullet-}$ [32]), it cannot be ruled out that DMPO/OH or
257 DMPO/2OH resulted from DMPO-SO₄ hydrolysis [33].

258 The scavenging experiments using distinct organic compounds to assess the
259 presence of hydroxyl and sulfate radical species were carried out using isopropyl
260 alcohol and t-butyl alcohol, respectively, as seen in Fig. 5a. As expected to attest the
261 presence of both radicals, the use of isopropyl alcohol (similar second-order kinetic
262 constants with HO• and $\text{SO}_4^{\bullet-}$ species, *i.e.*, $2.8 \times 10^9 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $6 \times 10^7 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$
263 [34] – see Table 2) led to a complete cessation of IMD oxidation. On the other hand,
264 when t-butyl alcohol was used, which is more selective towards HO• (the second-order
265 rate constant is in the range of $3.8\text{-}7.6 \times 10^8 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$, whereas for the reaction

266 involving $\text{SO}_4^{\bullet-}$ radical, it is significantly lower, ranging from 4 to $9.1 \times 10^5 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$
267 [34]), IMD oxidation decreased resulting in 30% after 6 h. Clearly, both radical species
268 are present in the reaction mixture.

269 Concerning the presence of $^1\text{O}_2$, the oxidation of IMD did not occur with the use
270 of furfuryl alcohol as scavenger (refer to Fig. 5a); however, the literature has shown that
271 furfuryl alcohol can react directly with PMS [35,36]. Thus, taking into account the
272 deactivation of singlet to triplet oxygen, measurements of dissolved oxygen were
273 carried out as shown in Fig 5b. Clearly, when Cu(II) ions in the presence of PMS were
274 analyzed, the amount of dissolved oxygen increased (deactivation of $^1\text{O}_2$ to $^3\text{O}_2$) and
275 remained higher in comparison to the buffered solution or even in the sole presence of
276 the buffer solution and PMS. Therefore, the Cu(II)/PMS system is also generating $^1\text{O}_2$
277 species.

278 To gain further information about the possible role of Cu(I) and Cu(III) species
279 in the activation of PMS, as suggested in the work of Wang et al. [20], a series of
280 experiments were carried out using neocuproine (NCP) and periodate. The latter can
281 complex with Cu(III) species leading to an absorption peak at 415 nm and the former is
282 a specific chelating compound of Cu(I) species. As observed in Fig. 5c, the use of NCP
283 (previously dissolved in 5 mmol L^{-1} of methanol) resulted in a complete cessation of
284 IMD oxidation, probably due to the participation of Cu(I) in the activation of PMS. As
285 methanol can also scavenge HO^\bullet species (depending on the concentration), a blank
286 experiment in the sole presence of 5 mmol L^{-1} of methanol (without NCP) was carried
287 out and exhibited no inhibition of IMD oxidation. To assess the presence of Cu(III)
288 species, we carried out similar experiments using sodium periodate. As expected, the
289 oxidation of IMD was entirely suppressed, leading to the observation of a broad band at
290 416 nm (please refer to Fig. S8). This is indicative of the complex compound that forms

291 as a result of the interaction between Cu(III) and periodate ions; however, that band was
292 only observed when using 2 mmol L⁻¹ of Cu(II) (see experimental conditions in Fig.
293 S8). When nitrobenzene (0.2 μmol L⁻¹ in 5 mmol L⁻¹ CH₃OH) is used to scavenge HO•
294 radicals, as Wang et al. [22] also described, only a marginal reduction in the reaction
295 rate is observed. Consequently, the generation of Cu(III)/Cu(I) species and their
296 potential involvement in IMD oxidation appears to be plausible.

297 Additional insight into the role of Cu species in IMD oxidation is obtained from
298 the experiment conducted using 5 mmol L⁻¹ CH₃OH. In this scenario, a complete
299 cessation of IMD oxidation would be expected, given that the calculated steady state
300 concentration of HO• is around 1.96×10^{-14} mol L⁻¹ (taking into account that the second
301 order kinetic constant of reaction between HO• and IMD is 1.0×10^{10} L mol⁻¹ s⁻¹ [37] –
302 see Table 2) and the second order kinetic constant between CH₃OH and HO• is $9.7 \times$
303 10^8 L mol⁻¹ s⁻¹ [38]. As depicted in Fig. 5d, if the theoretical IMD decay is computed
304 based on the kinetic constants between IMD and HO•, IMD and SO₄•⁻, or both, the
305 resulting lines deviate significantly from the experimental values (control or when using
306 5 mmol L⁻¹ CH₃OH). Therefore, we hypothesize that the observed slight increase in the
307 reaction rate may be attributed to the contributions of Cu species (Cu(III)/Cu(I)), as
308 PMS alone or ¹O₂ seem to be incapable of oxidizing IMD (see Fig. 1a). The potential
309 hydrolysis of Cu(III) to generate HO• was evaluated through an experiment employing
310 0.2 μmol L⁻¹ nitrobenzene (see orange symbols in Fig. 5d). Evidently, a minor reduction
311 in IMD oxidation was achieved. Finally, when distinct amounts of Br⁻ ions (at 10 and
312 100 mmol L⁻¹) are used, which also lead to a specific reaction with HO• and SO₄•⁻
313 species (see Table 1), the oxidation of IMD did not occur. In contrast, Feng et al. [39]
314 reported an increase in the oxidation of methylene blue, which they attributed to the
315 possible formation of Br•/Br₂•⁻ resulting from the reaction with Cu(III) at pH 7. While

316 the presence of Cu(I) and Cu(III) species is well-established in the literature, their
317 contribution to IMD oxidation appears marginal within our tested experimental
318 conditions. This is because Cu(III) species may decompose to produce HO[•], and the
319 kinetic constants (which are pH-dependent) are lower than those associated with HO[•]
320 [40].

321

322 **4. Conclusions**

323

324 Complete oxidation of imidacloprid insecticide was attained in the presence of
325 both peroxymonosulfate (at concentrations higher than 500 μmol L⁻¹) and Cu(II) ions at
326 slight alkaline solutions (pH 8). When using tap water, the Cu(II)/PMS system was able
327 to oxidize IMD; however, the presence of inorganic and organic compounds commonly
328 found in real matrices negatively affected the oxidation of IMD.

329 The main detected oxidation byproducts resulted mostly from hydroxylation and
330 rupture of the imidazolidine ring, which also resulted in less harmful compounds based
331 on theoretical predictions made with the ECOSAR software.

332 The primary working oxidants produced were radical (mainly HO[•] and SO₄^{•-})
333 and non-radical (¹O₂, Cu(I), and Cu(III)) species. Among these, HO[•] seems to play a
334 significant role on IMD oxidation apart from Cu ion species, as assessed by scavenging
335 experiments, theoretical decay lines, and mass detection of the produced DMPO
336 byproducts.

337

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339

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- 523

Tables

525

526

527 **Table 1** Estimated acute and chronic toxicity data for IMD and its initial oxidation by-
 528 products (with elucidated structure) predicted by the ECOSAR software. The toxicity
 529 values can be classified according to Globally Harmonized System of Classification and
 530 Labelling of Chemicals (GHS), summarized in Table S5.

531

<i>m/z</i> compound	Acute toxicity		Chronic toxicity	
	LC50 / mg L ⁻¹		ChV / mg L ⁻¹	
	Fish	Daphnid	Fish	Daphnid
256.0569 (IMD)	5.13	2.81	5.21	0.218
230.0418 (P1)	6.19	3.15	10.3	0.316
272.0518 (P2)	12.2	5.45	47.3	0.857
288.0463 (P3)	23.3	8.99	243	2.38
157.9985 (P4)	21.1	12.8	10.9	0.694

532 Legend: Very toxic (red), Toxic (orange), Harmful (yellow) and Not harmful (green)

533 Halopyridines were chosen for the ECOSAR class, due to the lower values encountered for LC50 and
 534 ChV

535 For P2 and P3, the obtained results are independent of the hydroxyl group position

536 ChV = Chronic values

537 LC₅₀ = concentration of a chemical in air or of a chemical in water which causes the death of (50%) of a
 538 group of test animals - available at:

539 https://www.unece.org/fileadmin/DAM/trans/danger/publi/ghs/ghs_rev07/English/ST_SG_AC10_30_Re
 540 [v7e.pdf](https://www.unece.org/fileadmin/DAM/trans/danger/publi/ghs/ghs_rev07/English/ST_SG_AC10_30_Re)

541

542 **Table 2** Documented rate constants for the interaction of organic pollutants with
 543 reactive oxygen species

544

Compound	$k(\text{HO}\cdot)$ / L (mol s ⁻¹)	$k(\text{SO}_4^{\bullet-})$ / L (mol s ⁻¹)	$k(^1\text{O}_2)$ / L (mol s ⁻¹)	$k(\text{Cu(III)})$ / L (mol s ⁻¹)
Furfuryl alcohol	1.5×10^{10} [41]	n.a.	1.2×10^8 [42]	n.a.
Methanol	9.7×10^8 [38]	2.5×10^7 [43]	3.0×10^3 (in CCl ₄) [41]	4.9×10^7 [22] or $< 1 \times 10^6$ [40] at pH 5.4
Isopropyl alcohol	2.8×10^9 [34]	6×10^7 [34]	3.0×10^3 (in CCl ₄) [41]	n.a.
t-butyl alcohol	$3.8\text{--}7.6 \times 10^8$ [34]	$4\text{--}9.1 \times 10^5$ [34]	1.8×10^3 in CCl ₄ [41]	1.8×10^7 [19]
Nitrobenzene	3.9×10^9 [38]	$< 10^6$ [44]	n.a.	n.a.
Br ⁻	1.1×10^{10} [45]	3.5×10^9 [46]	n.a.	$< 1 \times 10^6$ (pH 5.4) [40]
IMD	1.0×10^{10} [37] 2.42×10^{10} [27]	$3\text{--}3.5 \times 10^8$ [47] 2.33×10^9 [27]	5.5×10^6 [48]	n.a.

545 *n.a. = not available

546

FIGURE CAPTIONS

547

548

549 **Fig 1 a)** IMD fraction and **b)** PMS consumption as a function of treatment time (t) for
550 distinct amount of PMS (see inset – concentrations refer to PMS) used during its
551 activation by Cu(II) ions. Conditions: $[\text{Cu(II)}] = 800 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ ($12.5 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$), $[\text{IMD}] =$
552 50 mg L^{-1} , 100 mL of solution, and using 10 mmol L^{-1} of $\text{Na}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ (pH 8 –
553 continuously monitored) as buffer at 25 °C. Error bars represent the standard deviation
554 derived from two repeated measurements, except for the oxidant consumption.

555

556 **Fig 2 a)** IMD fraction and **b)** PMS consumption as a function of treatment time (t) for
557 distinct values of investigated pH (see inset) during PMS activation by Cu(II) ions.
558 Conditions: $[\text{Cu(II)}] = 800 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ ($12.5 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$), $[\text{PMS}] = 500 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$, $[\text{IMD}] = 50$
559 mg L^{-1} , 100 mL of solution using 10 mmol L^{-1} of $\text{Na}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ (pH 8-10) or KH_2PO_4 (pH
560 7) as buffer at 25 °C. pH values were continuously monitored. Error bars represent the
561 standard deviation derived from two repeated measurements, except for the oxidant
562 consumption.

563

564 **Fig 3 a)** IMD fraction and **b)** PMS consumption as a function of treatment time (t) for
565 distinct water matrices (see inset) during PMS activation by Cu(II) ions. Conditions:
566 $[\text{Cu(II)}] = 800 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ ($12.5 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$), $[\text{PMS}] = 500 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$, $[\text{IMD}] = 50 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$, 100
567 mL of solution using 10 mmol L^{-1} of $\text{Na}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ (pH 8 – continuously monitored) as
568 buffer at 25 °C. Error bars represent the standard deviation derived from two repeated
569 measurements, except for the oxidant consumption.

570

571 **Fig. 4** Proposed fragmentation route for the IMD insecticide oxidation through PMS
572 activation by Cu(II) ions. Conditions: [Cu(II)] = 800 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ (12.5 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$), [PMS] =
573 500 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$, [IMD] = 50 mg L^{-1} , 100 mL of solution using 10 mmol L^{-1} of $\text{Na}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$
574 (pH 8 – continuously monitored) as buffer at 25 °C.

575

576 **Fig 5** IMD fraction (**a, b and d**) and **c**) evolution of the dissolved oxygen as a function
577 of treatment time (t) during PMS activation by Cu(II) ions. See the inset for details on
578 experiments carried out in the presence of scavenging compounds. The theoretical lines
579 on d) were calculated based on the kinetic constants of Table 1 (see text) and on the
580 steady state concentration of $\text{HO}^\bullet/\text{SO}_4^{\bullet-}$ species ($1.96 \times 10^{-14} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$). Conditions:
581 [Cu(II)] = 800 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ (12.5 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$), [PMS] = 500 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$, [IMD] = 50 mg L^{-1} , 100
582 mL of solution using 10 mmol L^{-1} of $\text{Na}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ (pH 8-10) or KH_2PO_4 (pH 7) as buffer at
583 25 °C. pH values were continuously monitored.

584